

Q2NS: A Modular Framework for Quantum Network Simulation in ns-3

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INVITED PAPER

Abstract—Quantum network simulators are essential for the design and evaluation of quantum network architectures and protocols. However, developing an effective simulator is particularly challenging due to the stateful and non-local nature of quantum entanglement, which requires persistent state awareness and tight in-network coordination. Moreover, because quantum communication protocols inherently rely on classical signaling, a realistic simulator must seamlessly integrate classical and quantum communication primitives within a unified framework. In this work, we present *Q2NS*, a modular and extensible quantum network simulation framework built on top of ns-3. The architectural design of *Q2NS* enforces a clear separation of concerns between the operational functionalities of modules and entities and the overarching control logic, enabling easy adaptation to heterogeneous and rapidly evolving Quantum Internet paradigms while leveraging ns-3’s mature classical networking stack. Additionally, *Q2NS* includes a dedicated visualization tool to facilitate developing an intuitive understanding of entanglement-based quantum networking. This design enables accurate modeling of entanglement dynamics and protocol control logic, by providing a flexible, open, and scalable platform for advancing the Quantum Internet research.

Index Terms—Quantum Network Simulator, ns-3, Quantum Internet, Entanglement, ERC-CoG QNattyNet.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of a fully operational Quantum Internet [1]–[5] promises transformative applications across secure communications [6]–[8], distributed quantum computing [9], [10], and high-precision sensing [11]–[13]. Yet, progress toward a functional Quantum Internet remains hindered by the prohibitive cost and technological immaturity of quantum hardware [14]–[17]. As a result, realistic and accessible simulation tools have become essential for the exploration of quantum network architectures, protocols, and control mechanisms. Such tools enable researchers to model, analyze, and validate complex quantum communication scenarios within controlled and reproducible environments. They facilitate rapid prototyping, quantitative performance evaluation, and exploration of new design principles, bridging the gap between theoretical design and practical implementation.

This work has been funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe ERC-CoG grant QNattyNet, n.101169850. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

However, designing an effective simulator for quantum networks is far from trivial due to the unconventional principles and phenomena of quantum mechanics: qubits cannot be copied, quantum states degrade rapidly, and local operations can have non-local effects when acting on entangled states [14], [18]. Indeed, entanglement – the key resource of any quantum network – is inherently non-local and stateful: local actions on one node can instantaneously affect correlated states across distant nodes. Consequently, a credible simulator must be capable of maintaining a persistent, global awareness of the overall quantum state, while enabling tight in-network coordination to capture these non-local interactions. Moreover, since the entire life-cycle of entanglement – spanning its generation, distribution, and exploitation – together with other quantum communication protocols, relies on classical signaling for synchronization, control, and coordination [14], [15], [19], an effective quantum network simulator must seamlessly integrate both classical and quantum communication primitives within a unified architectural design. At the same time, accurately capturing quantum phenomena is computationally challenging, as the simulatability of quantum systems on classical hardware is fundamentally limited by the exponential growth of the quantum state-space with the qubit number.

From all of the above, it is evident that *the design of the simulator architecture is itself a determining factor in achieving both accuracy and scalability*, even before the implementation of individual software modules or libraries. A well-designed framework must capture not only event-driven dynamics, but also the global control logic governing the life-cycle of entangled states. Without such architectural coherence, a simulator cannot faithfully reproduce the operational constraints and resource dependencies that define entanglement-based networking.

We take a first step toward addressing these challenges, by presenting *Q2NS*, a modular and inherently extensible quantum network simulation framework, built on top of ns-3, a discrete-event classical network simulator [31]. *Q2NS* is designed to natively support the inherent interplay between quantum and classical communication primitives, within a unified architecture. This, in turn, ensures accurate modeling of entanglement dynamics and control logic. As detailed in Sec. II, the architectural design of *Q2NS* enforces a clear separation of concerns between the operational functionalities of modules and entities and the overarching control logic.

TABLE I: Comparison of selected quantum network simulators

Simulator	Language(s)	Open Source	Classical Stack	Timing Realism	Extensibility	General Purpose
SQUANCH [20]	Python	✓	Limited	Limited	Moderate	×
QuNetSim [21]	Python	✓	✓	×	High	✓
NetSquid [22]	C++/Python	×	×	✓	Limited	✓
SeQeNCe [23]	C++/Python	✓	×	✓	Moderate	✓
NetQASM SDK [24]	C++/Python	✓	Limited	Limited	High	×
QNE-ADK [25]	C++/Python	×	Limited	Limited	High	×
QuiSP [26]	C++	✓	Limited	✓	Moderate	✓
QKNetSim(+) [27], [28]	C++ (ns-3)	✓	✓	✓	Limited	×
ns-3 Quantum Network Module [29]	C++ (ns-3)	✓	✓	✓	Moderate	×
qns-3 [30]	C++ (ns-3)	✓	✓	✓	Moderate	✓
Q2NS	C++ (ns-3)/Python	✓	✓	✓	High	✓

This enables flexible adaptation to heterogeneous and rapidly evolving Quantum Internet paradigms, while leveraging the mature classical networking capabilities of ns-3. Furthermore, its modular design facilitates extensibility, allowing researchers to incorporate new architectures, protocols, and quantum noise models with minimal effort.

Written in C++, *Q2NS* offers higher computational efficiency compared to Python-based alternatives, discussed in the related works. This efficiency stems not only from the use of a compiled language but also from the event-driven architecture and the memory-optimized design of ns-3. In addition, through the introduction of a dedicated visualization tool, *Q2NS* facilitates the development and intuitive understanding of quantum networking.

In summary, through its architectural principles and integration with ns-3, *Q2NS* aims at providing a flexible and scalable platform, accessible to a broad community of researchers across both quantum and classical communities. The contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- i. We introduce the *Q2NS* architectural principles, design rationale, and core modules;
- ii. We present the *Q2NS* visualization tool;
- iii. We take a first step toward validating the framework’s effectiveness through a hybrid quantum-classical networking case study and a comparative runtime analysis that demonstrates superior efficiency relative to another simulator under comparable conditions.

A. Related Works

Although several quantum network simulators have emerged in recent years, none fully balance both comprehensive physical accuracy and broad accessibility for the wider networking community, while embracing the need for centralized control logic. For instance, *NetSquid* [22] offers detailed modeling of quantum operations, noise, and event-driven simulation. However, it is closed-source and abstracts classical communication, without modeling the underlying network stack or transport protocols, rendering it ill-suited for detailed studies of the interplay between the Classical and Quantum Internet. *SeQeNCe* [23] provides modular quantum protocol stacks and discrete-event control, but is coupled to specific architectures and lacks native integration with classical network layers.

Taking a different approach, *QKNetSim* [27] and *QKNetSim+* [28] extend *ns-3* [31], a classical network simulator, with QKD primitives. However, the base simulator and its improvements are narrow in focus and do not actually model quantum mechanics. The recently developed *ns-3 Quantum Network Simulation Module* [29] extends ns-3 more deeply, but is currently specialized for QKD rather than built for general-purpose quantum network simulation. In addition, no available work presents its architectural design.

Qns-3 [30] takes this further with a general-purpose, tensor-network-based extension of ns-3. Tensor networks can be powerful in low-entanglement regimes, but their runtime grows rapidly in multipartite entanglement scenarios, which are common and critical in quantum networking. The authors mitigate this with Control Flow Adaptation (CFA), replacing measurements with case-specific unitaries that maintain compact tensor networks. However, this approach is extremely difficult to generalize and can depend on unfeasible abstractions, such as global qubit access. A preliminary comparative analysis between the proposed *Q2NS* and *qns-3* is presented in Sec. III. The above simulator comparison is summarized in Table I.

II. ARCHITECTURAL PRINCIPLES

Q2NS is largely inspired by recent advances in quantum network architectural modeling [1]. Indeed, the double “N” in *Q2NS* is not merely nominal, it reflects a fundamental design principle introduced in [1]. Specifically, the effective management and utilization of entanglement resources demand not only a well-defined architecture, but also a distinct network-control layer that is clearly decoupled from in-network operations [1]. Accordingly, *Q2NS* explicitly implements this decoupling, with the first “N” in the acronym referring to the network control and the second “N” to the in-networks operations, within a unified architectural framework. Building upon this foundational principle, the *Q2NS* architecture adheres to three key design tenets:

- *Separation of concerns*: each module is responsible for a specific class of functionalities, and does not depend on internal workings of other modules.
- *Abstraction*: each module exposes a well-defined interface, enabling controlled interaction among components.

Fig. 1: Graphical representation of the *Q2NS* simulation environment, illustrating the main entities (NetController, QNodes, QChannels) and their components. The diagram highlights the simulator’s modular architecture, the separation of concerns and the interactions between modules and their hierarchies within the simulation framework.

- *Flexibility*: the framework can be easily extended or modified, enabling new functionalities to be added or existing ones to be replaced as needed.

The following details how these architectural principles are instantiated within *Q2NS* through its modular design, centralized control layer, and integration with ns-3.

A. Entities and Modules

The core of our architecture is modularity. The simulator is designed as a collection of self-contained modules that neatly interact via well-defined interfaces. Each module encapsulates a distinct logical functionality and can be easily extended or replaced without affecting the rest of the system. This separation of concerns establishes a clear boundary between logical and implementation-specific functionalities, enabling straightforward replacement of system modules or control mechanisms. The main entities are represented in Fig. 1 and consist of: NetController, QNodes, and QChannels. Each entity is composed of different modules with their own specific class of functionalities:

- **NetController**: is the super-entity overseeing the simulation and capturing the need for centralized control logic. Its functionality is divided into two modules: the SimulationCore, which manages the simulation environment and coordinates initialization and module interactions, and the QStateRegistry, which maintains and provides access to the single source of truth for all quantum states in the network. States are represented by QState, which provides a unified interface supporting multiple quantum-state representations. It currently integrates three backends: ket and density matrices using *Quantum++* [32] and stabilizers using [33]’s quadratic form expressions approach. The design allows users to

easily extend this to additional state representations. In essence, the NetController is the orchestrator of the network.

- **QNode**: is the entity capable of performing quantum and classical operations within the network, regardless of its role as end-user, repeater, or intermediary. It contains two modules: QProcessor and QNetworker, reflecting the separation of concerns described in the following section. It inherits directly from the classical ns-3 Node class, allowing full participation in all classical networking operations, such as TCP/IP communication, without additional integration. In essence, QNode acts as a task executor within the simulation framework.
- **QChannel**: models the quantum physical medium between nodes. It simulates realistic quantum-state transmission via the QMap module. This applies a Completely Positive Trace Preserving (CPTP) map to model the channel’s effects on the transmitted state. Importantly, this process can degrade key physical properties such as fidelity and entanglement.

B. QProcessor and QNetworker

As aforementioned, QNode is constituted by two main modules:

- **QProcessor**: oversees the local quantum processing within a node. It performs typical local operations, including applying gates, measuring, and creating Bell pairs. In essence, the QProcessor is the brain of the QNode.
- **QNetworker**: oversees the quantum networking operations of the node. It transmits and receives qubits using a QNetDevice interfaced with a QChannel. This procedure mirrors the classical packet transmission mechanism in ns-3, as both QNetDevice and QChannel classes inherit directly from their classical ns-3 counterparts. In

(a) Fidelity of the teleported state $|+\rangle$ versus distance between Alice and Bob, for different values of T_{dep} and with idle or congested classical channels. Data is averaged over 1000 simulation runs with ± 1 standard deviation error bars.

(b) Comparison of qns-3 and $Q2NS$ runtimes for an entanglement swapping chain with increasing number of network nodes, demonstrating $Q2NS$'s higher performance. Error bars represent ± 1 standard deviation across independent trials.

Fig. 3: Simulation results of (a) teleportation fidelity under varying noise conditions and channel congestion and (b) simulator runtime efficiency of an entanglement swapping chain in $Q2NS$ versus qns-3.

Simulation Results. The simulation results are shown in Fig. 3a. Fidelities fit the theoretical value of the $|+\rangle$ state, $F_+(t) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + e^{-t/T_{dep}})$ with $R^2 \geq 0.997$, where R^2 denotes the coefficient of determination quantifying the agreement between the simulated and theoretical values [38]. Qualitatively, three trends further confirm the simulation's accuracy:

- i. In the noise-free scenario ($T_{dep} = \infty$), the fidelity remains constant at its maximum value of 1.0, regardless of the classical link length or congestion level.
- ii. In the noisy scenario ($T_{dep} = 5$ ms), the fidelity decreases with distance, with a significantly sharper drop under congested conditions, approaching the minimum value of 0.5 at long distances and high congestion levels.
- iii. TCP and UDP exhibit similar overall trends. However, TCP yields slightly lower fidelity in the idle-channel case. This is expected, due to the additional overhead of TCP and the absence of a warm-up phase, which introduces an inherent latency.

This simulation scenario highlights how classical network congestion directly impacts quantum fidelity due to increased decoherence during delayed classical communication. $Q2NS$ enables such an analysis with minimal effort, demonstrating its utility and effectiveness for studying the interplay between quantum and classical network infrastructure.

B. Qns-3 comparison

Due to the page-limit constraints, we present a preliminary comparative analysis with qns-3. Specifically, we consider a case study consisting of a sequence of entanglement-swapping operations across a chain of N nodes in a quantum network. The simulation runtimes obtained with $Q2NS$ are compared against those of qns-3, which incorporates CFA optimization.

Simulation setup. All experiments are conducted within a Dockerized Ubuntu 22.04 LTS environment, allocated 6 virtual CPU cores and 16 GB of memory, and executed on a MacBook Air equipped with an Apple M3 processor and 24 GB of unified memory. Independent trials for each N were repeated until the margin of error of the 95% confidence interval on the mean runtime remained below 2% for consecutive trials. In both simulators, the nodes share a single IPv6 CSMA LAN with static routing, where 1024-byte UDPv6 packets carry classical information. In $Q2NS$, these packets carry the Bell-State measurement results from each repeater to Bob. In qns-3, they are used only during the initial entanglement distribution step, and all subsequent operations proceed locally through quantum operations without further classical communication.

Simulation results. Qns-3 provides three implementations of entanglement swapping: one without and two with CFA. For instance, the basic version without CFA requires 1027 s for 16 repeaters, whereas the CFA-enabled versions reduce this dramatically to about 3 - 5 s [30]. Both CFA versions require violations of the no-signaling theorem, so we compare to the CFA version that requires fewer non-physical assumptions. All approaches retain all possible outcomes of each repeater's Bell-state measurements, with CFA encoding them coherently into non-physical, global qubits. This significantly increases computational overhead without affecting the logical result.

In contrast, $Q2NS$ samples only one measurement branch, achieving the same shared state between Alice and Bob orders of magnitude more quickly. For instance, it completes a single 16-repeater trial in approximately 4 ms. As the problem size grows, the qns-3 approach rapidly becomes unfeasible, taking over an hour for $N = 256$, whereas $Q2NS$ takes roughly 80 ms. Although Monte Carlo trials with $Q2NS$ would increase total runtime, its favorable scaling ensures that such simulations

remain substantially more efficient, as illustrated in Fig. 3b. Indeed, a preliminary scaling analysis suggests that the qns-3 CFA implementation of entanglement swapping scales as $O(N^3)$, while $Q2NS$ scales closer to $O(N^{1.5}) - O(N^2)$.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have introduced the architecture and design principles of $Q2NS$, an open-source, modular quantum network simulator built on ns-3. $Q2NS$ addresses the challenges of simulating realistic quantum networks and their interplay with classical networks, by providing a unified, flexible and extensible framework that integrates both quantum and classical primitives. The architectural modularity, separation of concerns, and centralized control enable rapid adaptation to emerging quantum networking paradigms and experimental requirements. Furthermore, the integrated visualization tool broadens accessibility, by illustrating quantum network and entanglement dynamics to a wider audience. The conducted simulation analysis highlighted several advantages of $Q2NS$, including (but not limited to) superior computational efficiency, as shown in comparative benchmarks against the tensor-network-based simulator qns-3. While a comprehensive cross-simulator evaluation is left for future work due to page-limit constraints, the design principles and initial results of $Q2NS$ suggest that it scales particularly well in large, high-entanglement regimes, where existing tools may face practical limitations.

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